

Career Model Psychological Counseling Skills for Homeroom Teachers at Secondary Schools in Dak Nong Province, Vietnam

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 18 July 2022</p>	<p>Counseling in school psychology involves mental health care for children, adults, and parents. This practice is crucial in assisting kids in finding balance in their lives and avoiding frequent psychological issues. This practice aims to assist pupils overcome obstacles to learning and get rid of bad feelings and beliefs. Additionally, it strengthens the bonds between families, instructors, and kids. The school counselor's responsibilities include helping students and families connect, assisting in the resolution of disputes, and fostering greater understanding among family members. They also assist teachers in better understanding student psychology so that students receive the proper education, teaching, and attention. The school counselor's responsibilities include resolving issues with communication, stress management, and learning; fostering relationships between students and families, assisting in the resolution of disputes and aiding in improved family communication; To provide proper instruction, teaching, and attention, aid teachers in their understanding of student psychology. The school counselor's responsibilities include resolving issues with communication, stress management, and learning; fostering relationships between students and families, assisting in the resolution of disputes and aiding in improved family communication; To provide proper instruction, teaching, and attention, aid teachers in their understanding of student psychology. preventing psychological illnesses that affect students in school, such as stress, anxiety disorders, nervous breakdowns, pressure to perform academically, emotional issues, being a victim of school violence, or being isolated. assist pupils in acquiring a typical personality. The development of a school counseling model is discussed in this study for homeroom teachers in Dak Nong province, Vietnam.</p>
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<p>KEYWORDS: Counseling school; school counselor's; student; learning; family communication</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

In the United States, school counseling emerged at the beginning of the 20th century as a subfield of psychological therapy. In Vietnam, student psychological therapy is receiving more attention and is crucial to the upbringing and support of students. The Ministry of Education and Training's Circular 31 on regulating the activity of psychological counseling for high school students highlights that counseling is psychological support that aids pupils in bettering their self-awareness. Making decisions independently in challenging situations children meet while studying at school depends on factors such as familial circumstances, social interactions, and other factors that increase good feelings. Particularly in the setting of a culture with numerous changes and detrimental effects on psychology, drawing students to various bad behaviors, an insensitive lifestyle, and the

development of abnormal personalities... As a result, school psychology counseling needs to be more accountable than before..

Since there is currently no school psychologist on staff, instructors in general and homeroom teachers in particular play a significant role in providing psychological counseling services to high school students. It is essential to give instructors training in psychological counseling in schools. Middle school students frequently experience psychological issues, and their homeroom teacher is the one who knows them best in school. Based on their knowledge of and expertise in psychological counseling, it can be claimed that the homeroom teacher is the one who carries out early intervention with pupils' psychological problems. Building a model to enhance psychological counseling abilities for technical instructors at secondary schools in Dak Nong

province is a current and urgent issue based on current urgent needs.

2. CONTENT

2.1. Model of psychological therapy in secondary schools in the province of Dak Nong

a. The model of school psychology counseling activities' objectives are as follows: Create a specific guide for the efficient implementation of psychological counseling activities by professional teachers for secondary school students in Dak Nong province. The goal is to build models of psychological counseling activities in secondary schools to meet the requirements, characteristics, and conditions of school psychology counseling.

b. The content of the school psychology counseling model at secondary schools in Dak Nong province

The creation of a plan, or a periodic program of activities for each semester and the entire school year, forms the foundation of the school counselor's work. The next step is to define the topics for school psychology counseling and choose the type of therapy with an eye toward avoiding and resolving psychological issues with perception, emotion, behavior, and physical health. social interactions and student learning. The process of psychological therapy needs to be ensured in a scientific approach, encouraging the clients secondary school students to self-discover their potential and find solutions to their issues.

The school counseling room, consultation time, and coordination of consultations are a few examples of the criteria that must be met in order for consultations to be organized in a way that supports good counseling activities. The foundation of trust for kids, schools, and society in the caliber of school counseling is crucial knowledge, qualities, and skills that school counselors must ensure when engaging in counseling activities.

The model for psychological counseling activities in secondary schools must be broad and connected with various forces in order to be implemented (CASP-I, 2011). The following procedure is part of this model:

First, the teacher determines the student's issue;

Step 2: Conduct a preliminary analysis of the student's issue;

Step 3: Consult with professionals or knowledgeable teachers;

Step 4: Create a unique student support plan;

Step 5: Giving students advice;

Step 6: Overseeing the school's student support team.

c. *Identify participants in school psychology counseling activities*

Activities for school counseling should be decentralized, with distinct powers and functions, as participants can be extremely diverse. Several educational factors must be coordinated in order to solve children's challenges. As a result, the following are the primary parts:

+ Department of Education and Training: Has general management and supervision responsibilities for school counseling activities at secondary schools; a staff member with expertise in psychology-education or school counseling and professional management must be assigned. Review, plan, and summarize reports.

+ Departments of education and training: Take on a distinct managerial role in school counseling initiatives. Select a staff member with experience in psychology-education, school counseling, or professional management; review, plan, and summarize the report...

+ A team of school psychologists consults with administrators, full-time teachers, homeroom teachers, parents, and students to determine the best support strategy for each student. Teachers in the psychological counseling team who have received training in professional school psychology knowledge and who possess the credentials and capabilities of school counselors are known as school psychology counselor teachers.

Particularly, there is a need for persons with school psychology experience in the management agency of the Department of Education and Training to manage, monitor, and advise the Department on policies on this activity as well as other educational activities based on school psychology.

In order to attain effectiveness and quality in education for the whole development of students' personalities, psychology teachers at schools carry out the direct task of school psychology counseling activities.

d. Model execution

(1) Detailed analysis of the actual situation at the school, including: resources of teachers, resources of facilities, and resources of support policies. Implement a specific model of psychological counseling activities in secondary schools.

(2) Create a model of psychological counseling activities for secondary schools with detailed descriptions and instructions on how to carry them out.

(3) Provide guidance for teachers and other people involved in the model's implementation. (4) This model must be compatible with the actual educational activities of the school as well as the conditions of the facilities. Homeroom teachers, homeroom teachers, and other educational forces all interact specifically in this process.

(5) Evaluation of model implementation effectiveness

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Figure 1. Operational model of student support groups (CASP-I, 2011)

e. Condition for model execution

(1) The school needs to have the facilities to support the model's implementation;

(2) the model's implementation must have the proper methods and policies.

(3) There is a department in charge of overseeing the deployment and implementation of models. Consider model implementation to be a required task.

(4) Availability of time and space plus a counseling room in the school:

+ It ought to be a separate space that carries out particular duties and is set up scientifically. The effectiveness of consultation is ensured through counseling; Guidance sessions at schools: A school counseling case takes an hour, and the counselor should choose this time well for the counselor himself so that it does not conflict with other activities.

+ School counseling session length: A school counseling session lasts an hour. This time should be set aside by the counselor for himself and the kids in the school so that the counselor may effectively reveal the problem with counseling and reach the desired level of effectiveness.

- Process for consultation activity

+ Create a school counseling plan for kids, parents, and teachers based on research on screening and identifying issues in psychological and educational settings for each school year, semester, and month. ages;

+ Creating/choosing assessment tools to identify various factors to enable accurate diagnosis of students' difficulties;

+ Educate yourself on how to approach kids: Information on students can be obtained from a variety of methods, but it is important to prevent information interference and bias by information, thus speaking with students directly is the best source of information. Activities

both within and outside of school should be used to naturally approach kids who need counseling, and there should be a strategy to encourage the need for consultation on the part of students.

- + Individual, group, and family therapy: Determine the type of counseling best suited to the student client's issue and psychological make-up;

- + Continual and concluding assessments for consultations

- + The task of keeping coded records and following up with pupils after the consultation.

f. Establishing working conditions and working regulations

- + Create working conditions based on ethical norms for psychological counseling. This rules board should be hung or placed in the consultation room to serve as a reminder to both the counselor and those taking part in the consultation activity.

- + Create a welcoming, dependable, safe, and respectful working environment, a place where students want to go after stressful school days and after mind-numbing experiences. The creation of a work environment involves more than just physical amenities; it also involves the school counselor's own attitude toward his or her job.

- + To create an efficient and scientific coordination between the psychological counseling team and other educational forces both inside and outside the school.

g. Examining and evaluating school counseling programs in secondary schools

- + Developing standards and evaluation standards based on science and the specific tasks of local consultation programs + Publishing standards and evaluation criteria

- + Providing guidance on how to meet the standards and criteria in the evaluation of consultation programs

- + Having a plan to periodically check and evaluate school counseling programs with the following components: plan, evaluation criteria, plan, and evaluation results

- + Additionally, there is a chance to support school counselors' professional capacity development through this monitoring.

2.2. Model for training teachers in Dak Nong secondary schools in psychological counseling

2.2.1. The training model's goals are as follows

Providing technical teachers in junior high schools in Dak Nong province with training to increase awareness and develop their psychological counseling skills is a crucial activity. It aims to achieve three main objectives: improving the educational quality of the institution, raising awareness among teachers, and meeting societal needs.

The junior high school teachers at Dak Nong secondary schools are being given the opportunity to practice various counseling techniques as part of a model for developing psychological counseling skills in secondary school

instructors. organizing activities for both individual and group psychological counseling in the classroom, as well as providing fundamental psychological counseling. At the same time, this improves psychological balance, the capacity to appreciate and comprehend others in general and students in particular and accept differences.

2.2.2. Topics and methods for enhancing the counseling skills of junior high school technology teachers in the province of Dak Nong

(1) Content

The model's content focuses on developing knowledge and abilities, as well as offering working methods and supporting approaches, in accordance with the established objectives. Specifically:

Content 1. A general introduction of self-regulation strategies and school counseling: Give homeroom instructors some broad information on school counseling strategies and some self-balancing skills to help them do a good job of offering psychological support to secondary school pupils. In particular, to assist teachers in understanding the fundamentals of school psychology counseling and their function in the classroom; to assist them in learning self-balancing strategies; and to simultaneously arrange self-balancing approaches.

Content 2. The counseling method, early trust-building techniques, and how to recognize important concerns in school psychology counseling: Give secondary school pupils understanding of the psychological counseling process and fundamental abilities, such as the ability to establish a rapport and recognize important issues in psychological therapy. The following six steps of a psychological therapy procedure are introduced in this topic (Tran Thi Minh Duc, 2009): Building connections and trust between homeroom teachers and students; gathering information and identifying problems; choosing solutions and creating an implementation plan; putting solutions into practice; evaluating and closing; and following up after completion. Additionally, homeroom teachers study and put into practice basic trust-building abilities (listening, observing, and problem-solving abilities).

Content 3. Questioning skills, empathy skills, silence handling skills and how to keep records of psychological counseling

For lower secondary homeroom instructors, impart knowledge and teach the basics of empathy, questioning techniques, how to handle silent circumstances, and record-keeping for psychological therapy. In particular, homeroom instructors are given instructions and experience in effective questioning techniques, empathy skills, and how to deal with silent circumstances. They are also given guidelines for documenting and keeping track of psychiatric treatment. These are crucial training materials that aid teachers in compiling the essential data, building relationships of safety and trust with pupils, and assisting pupils in becoming

conscious of their own identities and current events. Teachers can simultaneously benefit from student cooperation, open communication, and readiness to accept responsibility, which helps to change students' inappropriate behavior.

Content 4: Practicing psychological counseling for a specific case

The teacher might put the acquired information and abilities to use by applying psychological counseling knowledge to a student's case, or parents experiencing mental health issues in accordance with the 6-step psychological counseling method. To be more precise, the homeroom teacher is split up into groups of three with one issue that requires psychological counseling for students and parents at school (trained teachers will assume the roles of homeroom teacher, student, parent, and supervisor while also documenting the counseling process and techniques used). The training class held a circle discussion and provided comments on the psychological counseling process and techniques they had just encountered after the psychological counseling session.

b. The application procedure

The following steps must be taken in order to conduct psychological counseling training for effective teachers:

Step 1: Choose technical instructors who will take training sessions

Step 2: Before the training process, technical teachers are given information about the model.

Step 3: Using a paradigm that focuses on performing psychological counseling capacity training, experts (with experience in psychology-education) attend direct training.

Step 4: Determine the level of capacity building and arrange for indirect supervision, peer support, and supervision.

5. Determine whether the independent implementation process was successful.

Step 6: Support and follow-up.

2.2.3. The format and procedure for carrying out the training model's implementation

The way that the psychological counseling skills training program for technical instructors is implemented is concentrated, directly at the chosen school facilities in Dak Nong province, and planned in accordance with the activities of each knowledge module. After the training time, set up an indirect form to aid in the development of industrial teachers' abilities to provide psychological counseling.

The primary training techniques include group work, role-playing, experience, and presentation strategies. Additionally, there are activities that calm you down, stimulate your brain to get you more excited, and help you feel balanced in a training class setting.

2.2.4. Requirements for planning the training model's implementation

Regarding the timing and location, it is held for two days at specific school facilities to train junior high school teachers in psychological counseling abilities.

About the team taking part in the training: management, internal training to comprehend the program, and ten lecturers from the Department of Psychology-Education who have a Master's degree in psychology or higher in their professional background. They have experience in teaching, training, and providing psychosocial counseling. Two faculty members are in charge of helping one another in planning training at each school site.

Regarding documentation and learning resources: Training materials are developed to suit each topic in the training program on psychological counseling skills for secondary school teachers. They are based on theoretical and applied research. In addition to learning materials and tools to support the implementation of the training program, such as handouts, A0 paper, markers, sticky notes, projectors, speakers, etc., materials are printed and provided to the technical teachers participating in the training.

3. CONCLUSION

For instructors working as homeroom teachers at lower secondary schools in Dak Nong province, Vietnam, the model of cultivating and enhancing psychological counseling abilities for homeroom teachers has offered knowledge and originally created psychological counseling skills.

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